

Sican Culture religion

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Lambayeque or Sicán, built ceremonial and political centers in the forested and cultivation esplanades located between the La Leche, Lambayeque, Reque and Zaña rivers. It was subdivided into early, middle and late Sican according to the Shimada sequence (1995, 2014). The Lambayeque elites consolidated their social position in the metallurgical activity and the access to exotic goods such as Spondylus shells and emeralds (Shimada, 1995). His legendary god was called Naymlap and was recorded by Miguel Cabello de Balboa in 1586 (Alva, 2021).

Date Range: 900 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Sicán region

Region tags: Peru

Territory covered by the Sican during the Middle horizon to the Late Intermediate period (900 CE-1200 CE)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Shimada, Izumi. (2014). *Cultura Sicán : esplendor preincaico de la costa norte*. Cervantes, Gabriela. (trad). Fondo Editorial del Congreso del Perú, Lima, 2014
- Source 2: HEYERDAHL, THOR; SANDWEISS, DANIEL; NARVÁEZ, ALFREDO y MILLONES, LUIS. (1996). TÚCUME. COLECCIÓN ARTE Y TESOROS DEL PERÚ.
- Source 3: Shimada, Izumi; Shinoda, Ken-ichi y Ono Masahiro (Eds.). (2009). *The Golden Capital of Sicán: Precursor of the Inka Empire*. Tokyo Broadcasting System Television, Tokio, Japón.
- Source 1: Buitrón, Rubén. (2023). *Fardos lambayeque en El Brujo*. Catálogo de la colección. Fundación Wiese, Perú
- Source 2: Wester La Torre, Carlos. (2010). *CHOTUNA-CHORNANCAP " Templos, Rituales y Ancestros Lambayeque"*

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://fundacionbbva.pe/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/libro_000051.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Shimada, Izumi. (1995). *Cultura Sicán. Dios, riqueza y poder en la costa norte del Perú*. Lima: Fundación del Banco Continental para el Fomento de la Educación y la Cultura, Edubanco.
- Source 2 URL: https://repositorio.ulima.edu.pe/bitstream/handle/20.500.12724/4027/Carcedo_de_Mufarech_Paloma.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Source 2 Description: Carcedo de Mufarech, Paloma. (2017). *Personajes de élite en la orfebrería Sicán: deidades, linajes y ancestros*. En A. Aimi, K. Makowski y E. Perassi (Eds), *Lambayeque: nuevos horizontes de la arqueología peruana* (pp. 183-216). Milano: Ledizioni. urn:isbn:9788867055722
- Source 3 URL: https://www.academia.edu/29886569/Libro_Coloquio_Cultura_Lambayeque_en_el_contexto_de_la_costa_norte_del_Per%C3%BA
- Source 3 Description: Fernandez, Julio y Wester, Carlos. (2014). *CULTURA LAMBAYEQUE EN EL CONTEXTO DE LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ*
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.elbrujo.pe/catalogo/?paginate=1&cultural=10&objeto=161>
- Source 1 Description: *Catálogo de piezas arqueológicas de EL Brujo*

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://www.ledizioni.it/stag/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Lambayeque_web1.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Aimi, Antonio; Makowski, Krzysztof y Perassi Emilia (Eds.). (2017). *Lambayeque NUEVOS HORIZONTES DE LA ARQUEOLOGÍA PERUANA*.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327136307_La_presencia_LambayequeSican_en_el_desierto_de_Sechura_extremo_norte_del_Peru_prime
- Source 2 Description: Goepfert, Nicolas; Vasquez, Segundo y Gutierrez, Belkys. (2018). *La presencia Lambayeque/Sicán en el desierto de Sechura (extremo norte del Perú): primeros resultados de las excavaciones en Huaca Amarilla*. In book: *Actas III Congreso Nacional de Arqueología* (pp.29-38). Ministerio de Cultura
- Source 3 URL: https://www.academia.edu/33180010/El_Tumi_de_Lambayeque_The_Tumi_of_Lambayeque?sm=b
- Source 3 Description: Kauffmann Doig, Federico. (2016). *El Tumi de Lambayeque*. Quingnam 2, pp. 125-

–Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/ProyectoEspecialNaylampLambayeque>

–Source 1 Description: Web oficial de la Unidad Ejecutora Naylamp (Ministerio de cultura) Perú

–Source 2 URL: <https://bit.ly/diosesdelam>

–Source 2 Description: Narváez, Luis. (2014). DIOS DE LAMBAYEQUE INTRODUCCIÓN AL ESTUDIO DE LA MITOLOGÍA TARDÍA DE LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ.

–Source 3 URL: <https://bit.ly/librodec>

–Source 3 Description: Narváez, Luis. (2014). DIOS ENCANTOS Y GENTILES Introducción al Estudio de la Tradición Oral Lambayecana

Notes:

<https://www.facebook.com/ProyectoEspecialNaylampLambayeque/posts/pfbid0deaAmA2DhRXismB6B8vA5KmqurFSSYrsiYuG3R2Qi6p7rm5xkvxLiA>

–Source 1 URL: <https://bit.ly/librovyc>

–Source 1 Description: Alva, Ignacio. (2013). VENTARRÓN y COLLUD ORIGEN Y AUGE DE LA CIVILIZACIÓN EN LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ

–Source 2 URL: <https://bit.ly/chornanapesES> / <https://bit.ly/chornanapenEN>

–Source 2 Description: Wester La Torre, Carlos. (2015). CHORNANCAP*PALACIO DE UNA GOBERNANTE Y SACERDOTISA DE LA CULTURA LAMBAYEQUE*

–Source 3 URL: <https://bit.ly/librochch>

–Source 3 Description: Wester La Torre, Carlos. (2018). PERSONAJES DE ÉLITE EN CHORNANCAP UNA NUEVA VISIÓN DE LA CULTURA LAMBAYEQUE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Some discuss the Sicán-Chimú relationship and dynamics during the late intermediate period based on data and insights gained from 30 years of fieldwork in the Lambayeque region by the Sicán Archaeological Project under Shimada's direction (Shimada, 2008)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: During the Middle Sicán, the polity and religion suffered a rapid collapse starting around 1050 C.E and ending around 1100 C.E. The above events were soon followed by a series of cultural changes, most notable of which were the "purging" of the Sicán Deity images and relocation of the Sicán capital to El Purgatorio just 6.5 km southwest of Sicán (Shimada, 2008). Also, some researches discuss about the Chimú Conquest of Lambayeque, the Sicán Heartland, and Its Consequences

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: with the Chimu culture

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

- ↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There was a kind of protection and redistribution of status, goods and food
- ↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: As in many cultures, a kind of redistribution of goods and food for construction works is considered
- ↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - Yes
 - Notes: As the authors of the references mention, there is a political benefit in favor of the community through the administration of basic resources: water, marine, contact with other settlements within the same political sphere, etc.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
 – Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):
 – Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):
 – Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:
 – Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:
 – Yes

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are many Sicán elite tombs with a distinct range of relevance such as warriors, weavers, priests, among others.
 - ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 55000

Notes: Batan Grande Archaeological Complex, occupying an area of some 55 sq. km. in the small coastal valley of La Leche in North Peru, is known as a mecca of grave looting that has yielded a considerable quantity of gold funerary artifacts. See Shimada (1981). The Batan Grande-La Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons. *Journal of Field Archaeology*. Vol. 8, No. 4, pp. 405-446

Reference: Shimada, Izumi. "The Batan Grande-la Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 8, no. 4 (1981): 405-46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/529792>.

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 30

Notes: See Shimada, 1981.

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

- ↳ Tombs:
 - Sí
 - Notes: The east and west Tombs at Huaca Loro (Shimada, 2014), the warrior at Illimo (Martinez 2014), the weaver at Collud (Alva, 2013), the elite characters at Chotuna-Chornancap (Wester 2015).
- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are many cemeteries in the Sican region such as Batan Grande, San Jose de Moro (Prieto 2014) and Huaca Cao (Chicama valley, Buitron 2023). In the cemeteries the burial patterns differ, some are extended, seated (Jequetepeque and La Leche Valley) and others are bundles (Chicama Valley), in addition to the cranial deformations and the ceramics of the Huaco Rey.
- ↳ Temples:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Batan Grande, Tucume, Purgatorio
- ↳ Altars:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Devotional markers:
 - No
- ↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
 - Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

- ↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
 - Some public spaces
 - Notes: Architecture and goods (such as metal objects, pots, textiles, among others)
- ↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Vaso B Denver <https://acortar.link/dVskRO>
 - ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Vaso B Denver <https://acortar.link/dVskRO>
 - ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - Yes
 - Notes: linear or geometric elements (single stepped, double stepped, spiral stepped, concentric circles)

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - No
- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Likely, yes
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Plants and flowers (botany)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Transport (totora, wooden rafts)
 - Yes
 - Notes: tools (fishing, sowing, hunting)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: It is recorded that during the Middle Sican, the inhabitants suffered the catastrophic effects of the El Niño phenomenon before the beginning of the agricultural cycles.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: As in all Andean cultures, the landscape is important. In the case of Sican, within the Batan Grande Archaeological Complex (Pomac Historical Sanctuary) the sacred hill of Chaparrí is located (to the east) while, to the west, across the sea, is the sacred island of wolves. of Earth. In Tucume pyramids, the most important hill is Purgatorio (Narvaez, 2014). In addition, certain huacas are oriented from east to west like Lercanlech. On the other hand, in interval occupations, hills with access and control to channels such as Cerro Luya, Arena, Huaringa or Sapamé have always been used. Which are also used to establish control and production points (metal).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Following Prieto's research (2010, p.233) Shimada suggests that Batan Grande was constructed as a pilgrimage center. The act of pilgrimage would have maintained active communication networks and increased consciousness of belonging to a larger whole, reinforcing the tendency toward integration (Shimada 1981 :442). On the other hand, Go Matsumoto (2019) concludes that Huacas de Sican does not seem to have been a pilgrimage center in Silverman's terms. Rather, the site consists of a large public space for social gatherings and surrounding ancestral shrines, each associated with an elite lineage. This peculiar configuration of the site requires new definitions, not only of ancestor cult but also of pilgrimage site (p.71)

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel. "Approximating Lambayeque Political Configurations : A Perspective from the Site of San José De Moro, Jequetepeque Valley". *Comparative Perspectives of the Archaeology of Coastal South America* 12 (2010): 231-46. <https://repositorio.pucp.edu.pe/index/handle/123456789/191977>.

Reference: Shimada, Izumi. "The Batan Grande-la Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 8, no. 4 (1981): 405-46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/529792>.

Reference: Matsumoto, Go. "Was Huacas De Sicán a Pilgrimage Center?: Results from Compositional Analysis of Serving Vessels from the Great Plaza". In *Ceramics of the Indigenous Cultures of South America: Studies of Production and Exchange Through Compositional Analysis*, edited by Michael Glascock, 59-71. University of New Mexico Press, 2019.

https://www.academia.edu/40444249/Was_Huacas_de_Sic%C3%A1n_a_Pilgrimage_Center_Results_from_Compositional_Analysis_of_Serving_Ves:

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: It can be interpreted from the funerary pattern, burials of people that accompany the main sacrifice, even animals or luxury offerings.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: It depends a lot on the geographical location of the Lambayeque societies, since the burial pattern is different, some are extended on their backs, seated or bundled.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: Lambayeque Valley

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: Jequetepeque Valley

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: mummy bundles

Notes: Chicama Valley

Reference: Buitron, Rubén. *Fardos Lambayeque En El Brujo*. Catálogo De Colecciones. Lima, Peru: Fundación Wiese, 2023.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Based on x-ray analysis, the individual does not have a spine and one of the upper extremities, researchers such as Buitron (2023) suggest the possibility of secondary burials due to the treatment of the bundle such as EEBFA00000-62

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: The main burials of relevant figures were always accompanied by 1 or more secondary individuals.

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: mainly camelids (heads and legs)

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Always huaco rey pots, textile, metal gods, some shells

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: spondylus (shells), gold-silver-copper (metal), fake trumpets

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: musical instruments (quenanas), other tools (seamstresses), among others

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

- Yes
- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - No
- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - No
- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Could be during the early Sican. It is associated with Naimlap as a leader, "ruler" who turns into a bird when he dies.
 - Reference: Wester, Carlos, ed.. Naimlap: Memoria Lambayeque Y Materialidad Histórica. Edited by Carlos Wester. Lima, Peru: Apus Graph Ediciones, 2021.
 - ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In Balboa's chronicle it is mentioned that Naimlap had children and built buildings
 - ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: From the point of view that "he came from the sea to stay, have children, build and live among the Lambayeque"

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - Notes: As I mention before, during the early Sican, likely yes, because he lived among they
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Transmits a positive feeling among the population, of health, security and wealth
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is mentioned (in the chronicle) that after Naylamp's death, the Lambayeque spread that he had become a bird and the gods sent divine punishment (climatic effect) plus the Chimú conquest.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Associated with the rituals of the priests in other Huacas

↳ Only through monarch

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Likely yes, because we are referring to Naimlap, the divinity that according to the chronicles existed among the Lambayeque/Sican (see Cabello de Balboa)
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Based on the legend of Naimlap
 - Reference: Urban, Matthias, and Rita Eloranta. "Ñaimlap, the Birds, and the Sea: Viewing an Ancient Peruvian Legend Through the Lens of Onomastics". *Names* 65(3) (2017): 154-66.
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Reference: Cabello Valboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica. Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo, 1586*. <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica/page/n3/mode/2up>.
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - Reference: Cabello Valboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica. Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo, 1586*. <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica/page/n3/mode/2up>.
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Likely yes, "Este señor Naymlap con todo su repuesto vino á aportar y tomar tierra á la boca de un Río (aora llamado Faquisllanga) y auiendo allí desamparado sus balsas se entraron la tierra adentro deseosos de hacer asiento en ella, y auiendo espacio de media legua fabricaron unos Palacios á su modo, a quien llamaron Chot"
 - Reference: Cabello Valboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica. Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo, 1586*. <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica/page/n3/mode/2up>.
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Yes [specify]: in person, from the chronicle of Cabello de Valboa, Naimlap was a ruler who came by sea

Reference: Cabello Valboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica. Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo*, 1586. <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica/page/n3/mode/2up>.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes
Notes: Some gods are related to natural events (like rain) or relevant tasks (e.g. textile goddess)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not as explicit as with the Mochica

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: In El Brujo, much of the funerary evidence comes from the Lambayeque culture (Sicán), whose individuals buried in the front of the Huaca Cao Viejo, presented tabula-type cranial modeling. This is characteristic of the Lambayeque/Sican burials in the Chicama Valley, however it is different for other valleys. <https://www.elbrujo.pe/blog/las-cintas-modeladoras-el-artefacto-detras-de-las-famosas-deformaciones-craneanas>

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: As with most burials in the Andes, there are several sacrifices that accompany the main elite burials.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

Elites:

– Field doesn't know

Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Children were usually sacrificed to appease radical climate effects.

Foreign, slaves:

– Field doesn't know

Commoners:

– Field doesn't know

Elites:

– Field doesn't know

Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: With the political fall in Batán Grande and later in Tucume, the Lambayeque/Sican changed their center of power to El Purgatorio, carrying out ritual activities on a smaller scale.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: The first religious political center was the Batán Grande Archaeological Complex, which was abandoned and moved to Tucume. However, during the end of the Sican period, they were restricted

to El Purgatorio until the Chimú conquest.

- ↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Seeds such as Nectandra have been found in the burials of healers (Huaca La Pava). Nectandra seeds, also known as Amala or Espingo (Ishpingo), are very common to record in archaeological contexts: Moche, Lambayeque, Chimú and Inca; Montoya (2012) carried out a bio/phytochemical study of seeds from Chimú contexts and determined that these seeds belonged to the genus Nectandra of the Lauraceae family. He also compared them with modern seeds, obtained from herbalists and healers who call them "Amala", " (coast and northern mountains), "Matuc" or "Matuto" (northern jungle), being very rarely known by the name "Ishpingo"; "Although Montoya admits that it may have several names, he uses the name "Espingo", since apparently it is under this term that these seeds are mentioned in the chronicles. Information about the discovery in Huaca La Pava (Mochumí, Lambayeque) is also recorded, but the information has not been officially published.
 - Reference: Montoya, Maria. "ESTUDIO FITOQUÍMICO Y BIOQUÍMICO DE SEMILLAS PREHISPÁNICAS DE Nectandra Sp.". ECIPERU. Revista Del Encuentro Científico Internacional 4 (2012): 1-8. <https://www.academia.edu/8571198>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Sican was an expansionist state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Reference: Cervantes, Gabriela. URBAN LAYOUT AND SOCIOPOLITICAL ORGANIZATION IN SICÁN, PERÚ. Lima, Peru: University of Pittsburgh, 2020. <https://d-scholarship.pitt.edu/39139/7/Cervantes%20Final%20ETD.pdf>.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has not yet been determined in the investigations

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi. "The Batan Grande-la Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 8, no. 4 (1981): 405-46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/529792>.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Wester, Carlos, ed.. *Naimlap: Memoria Lambayeque Y Materialidad Histórica*. Edited by Carlos Wester. Lima, Peru: Apus Graph Ediciones, 2021.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi. *Cultura Sican: Dios, Riqueza Y Poder En La Costa Norte Del Peru*. Lima, Peru: Eubanco, 1995.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi. "Sicán Elite Tombs and Their Broader Implications". *Institute of Archaeo-metallurgy Studies* 18 (1992): 31-34. https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeo-metallurgical-studies/sites/archaeo-metallurgical-studies/files/iams_18_1992_shimada.pdf.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Prieto, Gabriel. "El Fenómeno Lambayeque En San José De Moro, Valle De Jequetepeque: Una Perspectiva Desde El Valle Vecino.". In *Cultura Lambayeque. En El Contexto Norte De La Costa Del Perú*, edited by Julio Fernández and Carlos Wester La Torre, 107-38, 2014. https://www.academia.edu/8966477/El_Fen%C3%B3meno_Lambayeque_en_San_Jos%C3%A9_de_Moro_valle_de_Jequetepeque_Una_perspectiva_

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi. *Cultura Sicán : Esplendor Preincaico De La Costa Norte*. Translated by Gariebla Cervantes. Lima, Peru: Fondo Editorial del Congreso del Perú, 2014.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, HEYERDAHL, THOR, DANIEL SANDWEISS, ALFREDO NARVÁEZ, and LUIS MILLONES. *TÚCUME. COLECCIÓN ARTE Y TESOROS DEL PERÚ*. Lima, Peru, 1996.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi, Ken-ichi Shinoda, and Masahiro Ono . *The Golden Capital of Sicán: Precursor of the Inka Empire*. Tokio, Japón: Tokyo Broadcasting System Television, 2009.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Wester , Carlos. *CHOTUNA-CHORNANCAP " Templos, Rituales Y Ancestros Lambayeque"*, 2010.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Paloma, Carcedo de Mufarech, and A. Aimi. "Personajes De Élite En La Orfebrería Sicán: Deidades, Linajes Y Ancestros". In *Lambayeque: Nuevos Horizontes De La Arqueología Peruana*, edited by K. Makowski , 183-216. Milano, Italia: Ledizioni, 2017.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Fernandez, Julio, and Carlos Wester. *CULTURA LAMBAYEQUE EN EL CONTEXTO DE LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ*, 2014.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Makowski , Krzysztof , and Emilia Perassi . *Lambayeque NUEVOS HORIZONTES DE LA ARQUEOLOGÍA PERUANA*. Edited by Antonio Aimi, 2017. https://www.ledizioni.it/stag/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Lambayeque_web1.pdf.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Goepfert, Nicolas, Segundo Vasquez, and Belkys Gutierrez. "La Presencia Lambayeque/sicán En El Desierto De Sechura (extremo Norte Del Perú): Primeros Resultados De Las Excavaciones En Huaca Amarilla.". In *Actas III Congreso Nacional De Arqueología*, 29-38. Lima, Peru: Ministerio de Cultura, 2018. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327136307_La_presencia_LambayequeSican_en_el_desierto_de_Sechura_extremo_norte_del_Peru_prime

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Kauffmann, Federico. "El Tumi De Lambayeque". *Quingnam* 2 (2016): 125-40.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Narváez, Luis. *DIOSES DE LAMBAYEQUE INTRODUCCIÓN AL ESTUDIO DE LA MITOLOGÍA TARDÍA DE LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ*, 2014. <https://bit.ly/diosesdelam>.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Narváez, Luis. *DIOSES ENCANTOS Y GENTILES Introducción Al Estudio De La Tradición Oral Lambayecana*, 2014. <https://bit.ly/librodec>.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Alva, Ignacio. *VENTARRÓN Y COLLUD ORIGEN Y AUGE DE LA CIVILIZACIÓN EN LA COSTA NORTE DEL PERÚ*, 2013. <https://bit.ly/librovyc>.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Wester, Carlos. *CHORNANCAP "PALACIO DE UNA GOBERNANTE Y SACERDOTISA DE LA CULTURA LAMBAYEQUE"*, 2015. <https://bit.ly/chornancapen>.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Shimada, Izumi, and Raffael Cavallaro. "Monumental Adobe Architecture of the Late Prehispanic Northern North Coast of Peru". *Journal De La Societé Des Américanistes*, 1985, 41-78. https://www.persee.fr/doc/jsa_0037-9174_1985_num_71_1_2252.

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Matsumoto, Go. "Was Huacas De Sicán a Pilgrimage Center?: Results from Compositional Analysis of Serving Vessels from the Great Plaza". In *Ceramics of the Indigenous Cultures of South America: Studies of Production and Exchange Through Compositional Analysis*, edited by Michael Glascock, 59-71. University of New Mexico Press, 2019. https://www.academia.edu/40444249/Was_Huacas_de_Sic%C3%A1n_a_Pilgrimage_Center_Results_from_Compositional_Analysis_of_Serving_Vessel

Reference: Sican Culture religion, Prieto, Gabriel. "Approximating Lambayeque Political Configurations : A Perspective from the Site of San José De Moro, Jequetepeque Valley". *Comparative Perspectives of the Archaeology of Coastal South America* 12 (2010): 231-46. <https://repositorio.pucp.edu.pe/index/handle/123456789/191977>.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Field doesn't know, Shimada, Izumi. "The Batán Grande-la Leche Archaeological Project: The First Two Seasons". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 8, no. 4 (1981): 405-46. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/529792>.

Reference: Yes, Wester, Carlos, ed.. *Naimlap: Memoria Lambayeque Y Materialidad Histórica*. Edited by Carlos Wester. Lima, Peru: Apus Graph Ediciones, 2021.

Reference: Yes [specify]: mummy bundles, Buitron, Rubén. *Fardos Lambayeque En El Brujo*. Catálogo De Colecciones. Lima, Peru: Fundación Wiese, 2023.

Reference: Yes, Urban, Matthias, and Rita Eloranta. "Naimlap, the Birds, and the Sea: Viewing an Ancient Peruvian Legend Through the Lens of Onomastics". *Names* 65(3) (2017): 154-66.

Reference: Yes, Cabello Valboa, Miguel. *Miscelánea Antártica. Una Historia Del Perú Antiguo*, 1586. <https://archive.org/details/miscelanea-antartica/page/n3/mode/2up>.

Reference: Yes, Cervantes, Gabriela. *URBAN LAYOUT AND SOCIOPOLITICAL ORGANIZATION IN SICÁN, PERÚ*. Lima, Peru: University of Pittsburgh, 2020. <https://d-scholarship.pitt.edu/39139/7/Cervantes%20Final%20ETD.pdf>.

Reference: Field doesn't know, Matsumoto, Go. "Was Huacas De Sicán a Pilgrimage Center?: Results from Compositional Analysis of Serving Vessels from the Great Plaza". In *Ceramics of the Indigenous Cultures of South America: Studies of Production and Exchange Through Compositional Analysis*, edited by Michael Glascock, 59-71. University of New Mexico Press, 2019. https://www.academia.edu/40444249/Was_Huacas_de_Sic%C3%A1n_a_Pilgrimage_Center_Results_from_Compositional_Analysis_of_Serving_Vessel

Reference: Field doesn't know, Prieto, Gabriel. "Approximating Lambayeque Political Configurations : A Perspective from the Site of San José De Moro, Jequetepeque Valley". *Comparative Perspectives of the Archaeology of Coastal South America* 12 (2010): 231-46. <https://repositorio.pucp.edu.pe/index/handle/123456789/191977>.

Reference: Sí, Montoya, Maria. "ESTUDIO FITOQUÍMICO Y BIOQUÍMICO DE SEMILLAS PREHISPÁNICAS DE *Nectandra Sp.*". *ECIPERU. Revista Del Encuentro Científico Internacional* 4 (2012): 1-8. <https://www.academia.edu/8571198>.